

Transformation of Congress from Elite to Mass Movement

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The Indian National Congress established with the backing of the British Government in 1885 rhymed well with official schemes and behaved most loyally in the period of its history. W.C. Bonnerji, the first president of the Congress, praised in hyperbolic terms, 'the civilizing rule of the Queen' and the rulers convinced with the trait of loyalty in the Congress fully reciprocated the sentiment.¹ Dadabhai Naoroji, the President of the Second Congress, particularly referred to the spirit of fairness, moderation and respect towards the Government.² The three cheers for the Queen Empress, the Viceroy, the Principal Governors and even Lieutenant Governor warmly and vehemently gave fully constituted conclusive evidence of the loyalty of the Congress to it.³ The twenty years following the establishment of the Indian National Congress were conspicuous by the absence of any basic claim for self-government. The Congress demands were confined to the extension of franchise and representative institutions and so on and its activities were limited to oratory and passing resolution in favour of reforms.⁴

The members of the Congress continued to hold unswerving faith in the British sense of justice and fair play and relied on propaganda in England in favour of India. They were strongly of the view that the maintenance of an agency in England was essential in order that the sentiments and desires of the Congress might be effectually brought before the parliament and the public of Great Britain.⁵ The Congress meetings of the summer campaign of 1890 were therefore, held in various parts of the United Kingdom to bring the question of Indian reforms before the British public.⁶

The fact was that the national movement in India had by now taken a purely constitutional and loyal direction and expressed through the Congress the legitimate hopes and requirements of the people.⁷

Lord Curzon by his political intolerance and undisguised contempt for the educated classes gave moral offence to the Indian Chiefs and lost the regard and goodwill of the intelligentsia and gave rise to feelings of anger, disquiet and unrest throughout the country.⁸ Of all his acts, the worst was the partition of Bengal in 1905. This idea of territorial redistribution undoubtedly did not originate with him.⁹ But he actually brought it about and his

chief motive in doing so was to strike a nail in Bengali Nationalism by dividing its forces.¹⁰ Munshi Madholal regarded it as arbitrary, impolitic and unjust and Gokhale considered it a cruel wrong.¹¹ The Congress emphatically protested against it¹² and placed on record its unqualified condemnation of the detestable outrages committed in consequence of the project of partition.¹³

The cry arose that the Bengali nation has been insulted and split in twain. The sensational triumph of Japan over Russia having kindled the race consciousness of the East in the autumn of 1905, a very pretty campaign began to boycott an agitation.¹⁴ Secret societies were formed and avowed anarchism soon gained sufficient momentum.¹⁵ John Viscount Morley frankly accepted that the partition of Bengal was carried out against the strong wishes of the people concerned.¹⁶

The partition of Bengal led to far reaching results. It was the first organized agitation sustained for a long period and spread over a large territory. It did more towards strengthening the feeling of nationality throughout India than any other cause during the last fifty years.¹⁷ It brought the whole of the dormant potentiality of the country to the fore and the courage of our countrymen rose to unparalleled heights. The movement for the use of Swedish goods gave a powerful encouragement to Indian industries and expectations were entertained that it would ultimately usher in the day when the Indian would be recognized as a nation.¹⁸ The people of India found an opportunity in the Swadeshi Movement to make themselves respected by the whole world.¹⁹ In short, the results which could not be attained by other countries, even through long struggle and maximum efforts, reached their high water mark in a few days in India.²⁰

Such an outburst of national feelings created an atmosphere for a change of methods on the part of the Congress. The first ominous sigh of the movement had unmasked itself in the Benaras Congress held in December, 1905 when the boycott of the English goods was declared to be legitimate. The new movement started in 1905, reached its second stage in Calcutta where there was a stormy session and an open rupture was averted only by the tact and authority of Dadabhai Naoroji. But the relations between the Extremists and the Moderates became strained almost to the breaking point in 1906.²¹ However, in 1907 at Swat the most impatient spirits broke away from their former leaders and sought salvation in other directions and by other methods with the result that the session had to be suspended amidst tumultuous and unedifying scenes.²²

This new school associated with the leadership of Bal Gangadhar Tilak, popularly

known in history as the Extremist, was characterized by the spirit of self-reliance and opposition to western ways. Tilak realized the value of the study of national heroes, what if a nation feels the thrill of re-awakening after ages of slumber.²³ The Congress preached the growth of indigenous industries and advised the use of Indian products to the exclusion of imported commodities even at a sacrifice.²⁴ The Congress however, became somewhat more vocal now than before in advancing the demand for India's self-government.

Congress from Microscopic to Mass Organisation

In the history of the Indian National Congress the period between 1918 and 1923 is of critical importance because of the transformation in its political and organizational character. The moderates, unable to cope with the upsurge of discontent, were pushed aside and the leadership of the movement passed on to the former extremist section which had, by this time, acquired preponderant influence on political opinion in the country. In this changed situation, the Congress adopted, as its new objective, "The attainment of Swarajya by the people of India by all legitimate and peaceful means²⁵ and along with it a programme designed to develop the capacity for self government among the Indian people. The non-cooperation movement launched in 1920 produced unprecedented political awakening and transformed the Congress organization. Between 1918 and 1923, the Congress organization was governed by two constitutions: from 1918 to 1920 by the constitution adopted in 1908, and from 1921 onwards by the new constitution adopted in 1920.²⁶ Between 1918 and 1920, these were – provincial Congress committees; Andhra, Bangal, Berar, Bihar and Orissa, Bombay, Burma, the Central Provinces, Delhi and Ajmer-Merwara, Madras, Punjab, Sindh, and the United Provinces. These were not organized on any single principle. Generally they were based on the administrative divisions of India, but exceptions were made as in the case of India, Meanwhile, Assam, a separate administrative unit, was under the jurisdiction of the Bengal P.C.C. The existing provincial units were reorganized into 21 linguistically homogenous provinces.²⁷ Their general organizational pattern was governed by the rules adopted by the working committee,²⁸ according to which each village with five or more Congress members would have a Congress unit whose task it was to carry out the Congress program in the village, above such village units would be task or circle units, then Taluka or tehsil units, and above them the District units. The district Congress committees in a province would elect the Provincial Congress committee, and the P.C.C. would elect its officers, a Chairman, a Secretary, a Treasurer, and four other members. Their task would be to conduct the day-to-day affairs of the Congress in the province.

As part of the endeavor to bring the Congress closer to the masses, it was proposed in 1920 to conduct the proceedings of the Congress seniors as far as possible in Hindustani.²⁹ The Nagpur constitution decided on a paid membership drive. It was hoped that paid mass membership would provide the organization with a large part of the financial resources needed for its day-to-day work. The Congress acquired a large mass base in 1921. The year 1921, however, was one of exceptional activity. The non-cooperation movement led to a spectacular growth of Congress organization. The success of the Congress in widening its base is reflected partially in the number of peasant delegates attending its sessions. In 1918, for the first time, 688 of them, mostly from the United Provinces and the Punjab, attended the Congress session at Delhi, their number rose to 1,095 in 1919.³⁰ At the end of the first world war, the imminent threat to the Khalifa of the Islamic community brought the Indian Muslims actively into the nationalist movement and, because of the close alliance that resulted between the Congress on the one hand and the Muslim League and the central Khilafat committee on the other, a large number of Muslims entered the Congress.³¹ In fact, the Congress retrieved the support of the religious leaders of Indian Islam throughout its subsequent struggle for Independence. One of the notable achievements of the Congress movement in this period was to draw increasing numbers of women into its fold.

For many years from its inception, the Congress movement was centered in the main cities and provincial towns of India. The non-cooperation movement affected a dramatic reversal of this position. The Congress leadership was still composed largely of those who had taken to the new professions of law, journalism, teaching and western medicine. A few businessmen and fewer landowners were also represented. The monopoly of lawyers in the leadership was broken after the launching of non-cooperation in September 1920. In 1921, they were presented with the choice of retaining their positions in the Congress by renouncing the practice of law or retiring from public life.³²

A great many preferred to adopt the latter course. Among those who did not were C.R. Das, Motilal Nehru, C. Rajagopalachari. Thus the leadership was elected by the test of sacrifice as well as by the criteria of education and social status. The transformation was brought about in the professional composition of A.I.C.C. between 1919 and 1923.³³ Some of the most notable Congress leaders practiced journalism or established newspapers of their own to propagate the Congress cause. Mahatma Gandhi, Maulana Azad, Mohammad Ali, Rajendra Prasad, C. Rajagopalachari, T. Prakasan and C.R. Das established daily newspapers, but did not engage in journalism themselves.³⁴

The significant difference between the pre-1920 and the post-1920 Congress leadership lay in the fact that before 1920 it was social position which automatically conferred a leading role in the movement; after 1920 it was the renunciation of social position and the demonstration of willingness to accept sacrifice that was demanded of those who aspired to lead.³⁵ It was through their national outlook and renunciation of their privileges that Congress leaders, even though by caste and education they belonged to a small section of the population, came to represent the nation and not only their own class.³⁶

The Indian National Congress represented a broad national front, and not a tightly organized party. Gandhiji compared it with the British Parliament. "...I do not consider Congress as, a party organisation, even as the British Parliament though it contains all parties and has one party or other dominating it, from time to time, is not a party organisation."³⁷

The Congress provided a platform for all "parties" in the sense of subsidiary groups within the larger organization to appeal to the nation with a view to moulding its politics. It was, therefore, like a coalition consisting of different elements which agreed on general aims and methods but not always on specific items of policy or program.³⁸

Two consequences followed. The Congress organization could not be rigid and discipline was always loose. Gandhiji enunciated the doctrine that the decisions of the Congress were not binding on members, especially if they involved matters of conscience.³⁹ The degree of latitude permitted to dissenters was exceptionally wide, forbidding them only to act in the name of the Congress in a way contrary to its official policy.⁴⁰ While the freedom of opinion and action was given to the members, the same was not permitted to the office-holders of the organization. They were appointed to execute Congress policy and only those who accepted fully could be expected to do this. Gandhi insisted on rigorous enforcement of this elementary principle.⁴¹ Thus, after the adoption of the non-cooperation program, Gandhi urged that no practising lawyer could be allowed to head office in the organisation :

"If we do not face the issues boldly, we stand in danger of corrupting the movement. We must exact correspondence between percept and practice. I hold that a lawyer President of a provincial Congress cannot lead his province to victory, if he does not suspend his practice, he simply will not carry weight."⁴²

His view did not go unchallenged,⁴³ nor was it always enforced with the vigour he

demanded. But by and large it prevailed. The result was that while the Congress, as a whole, retained its loose and democratic character, it acquired a strong executive arm which gave effect to the official policy.⁴⁴ The second consequence was the acceptance of some limitations on Congress policies. Because the disparate groups it brought together in many cases had conflicting interests, it could not take up issues of sectional concern, even if in some instances many Congressmen happened to sympathize with one side or the other in a conflict between two groups within the movement.⁴⁵

The organization, as it emerged after 1922, became a powerful instrument of India's freedom struggle in the next twenty-five years. Though founded by persons belonging to educated, professional and business classes and dominated by upper caste Hindus, the Congress soon developed into a national movement, with organizational links extending far into the country and its support coming from wide sections of the population.⁴⁶ During sixty years of incessant activity it had striven to create a national community out of a people organized on the basis of caste and religion by securing the participation of an even increasing number of persons from different strata of society in the political struggle it led.⁴⁷ The independence movement was the principal instrument of political socialization in India.⁴⁸ Membership of it in the pre independence period could not be the passive act it later became; it was an active commitment to the wider society that was being created.

The Congress decision to use Indian languages in the deliberations of its provincial units and to propogate Hindi as a national language was governed by the same desire to draw the common people into the political movement and to provide the emerging nation with a language which could assist the process of integration. While at an earlier phase of political development the English language had served as a bridge between different sections of the emerging modern elite, by 1920 it had become a barrier between them and the masses. By taking the movement closer to the people and by making regional languages the medium of political communication, the Congress broke this barrier and greatly extended its support base.⁴⁹ The Congress had relatively few adherents among the minority communities, especially the Muslims, but true to its ideal and always aware that Indian society was more sharply divided by parochial sentiments than united in secular pursuits, it resisted sectarianism in politics and through determined secularism remained a national movement inspite of its largely Hindu composition.

Through its mass movements between 1920 and 1945, the Congress built for itself a position of unrivalled authority in the Indian part of the subcontinent. The immense power it

possessed was utilized by its pragmatic leadership to erect and then to sustain the new Indian state. The intellectual commitment of the Congress party to liberal values and its loose but comprehensive organization provided and continues to provide, the basis for the stable liberal policy of contemporary India.

Emergence of Gandhi-His Ideology and Conflicts

Gandhi's rise to the top of the Indian National Congress at the end of World War-I marks several important changes in its organization and programmes. During this time, there was also a shift in the balance of its leadership from Bengali and Maharashtrian dominance to a more even distribution with men from Gujarat and North India, playing a larger role than previously.⁵¹ At the same time, Gandhi led Congress began to tap new sources of support throughout India. The regional shift resulted in tensions and antagonisms which continue into the present.⁵² Leadership of a complex movement must be considered as having both negative and positive functions for the individuals and groups participating. Indian traditions especially in their solid regional variations, may be drawn upon to support a number of different nationalist ideologies and strategies.⁵³

Before Gandhi came to India with anti-imperialist attitude, Congress was designed to gear up the Indian National Movement. From the beginning, the Congress was conceived not as a party but as a movement. Gandhi was aware of the fact that Hindu Muslim unity and solidarity in the country was a pre-requisite to waging an anti-imperialist battle whole heartedly. To establish connectivity with common masses, he executed his value based politics which was his particular approach to inject cultural elements in politics to integrate all people of different religions, castes and sects. In the cultural aspect, religion plays a dominant role. And Gandhi used 'religion' also as a catalyst for mobilizing the masses and achieving their participation which gave the national movement a new dimension and momentum.

Gandhi's view was that Hindu-Muslim unity was in the interest of both and they would learn to live in peace. Gandhi was successful at Viramgam. He agitated against the system of indentured labour in Bombay. A deputation of ladies waited upon the Viceroy and ultimate success came through Satyagraha. At Champaran, Satyagraha was a great success and the age-long abuse created by Europeans planters came to an end in six months. Gandhi was also successful in getting workers of Ahmedabad Mill their due. Gandhi's part in the Khaira struggle was an outstanding example of his vindication of the rights of the Indian peasantry in its hour of acute suffering. All these events brought infinite fame to Gandhi.

Gandhi's ideologies of Satyagraha, non-cooperation, non-violence had a great impact on the Indian National Movement.

Non-Cooperation Decision and It's Impact

The non-cooperation movement in India was primarily a result of two forces – the first, the extraordinary personality of its author; the second, the post war restlessness which India shared with so many countries.⁵⁴ Without doubting in the least, the remarkable force of Gandhi's personality, it seems desirable to place the second as the first cause, for no movement would have been necessary at all had the post-war period not created circumstances favourable to the vindication of Indian honour.⁵⁵

During the period of World War I, India so greatly helped Britain with men, money and material that a demand in legislative Assembly in 1917 for compiling an elaborate and detailed report of the Indian contributions for publication after the war,⁵⁶ was interpreted by the British Government as having behind it the object to strengthen the hands of the Indian politicians in demanding political concessions.⁵⁷ Resolutions regarding post-war reforms were resolutely disallowed in the Assembly in 1917⁵⁸ and 1918⁵⁹. But owing to her sacrifices, India legitimately expected internal autonomy. However, what she got was the recommendation of the sedition committee conceding authority to the Government to demand security with or without sureties and the power of restricting residence. It also recommended arrest, search and confinement.⁶⁰

These recommendations formed the basis of the Rowlatt Act which gave the first shock to Gandhi as it was designed to rob the people of all real freedom.⁶¹ He realised that no state, however despotic, had the right to enact laws repugnant to the whole body of the people⁶² and felt sure that it was impossible to have real peace in India until the Rowlatt Act was repealed.⁶³ Even the British Committee of the Indian National Congress called attention to its reactionary character.⁶⁴ The blood of Amritsar, however, proved to be the seed of the now dynamic National Congress. From a policy of co-operation with the newly projected reforms, it swung round to non-cooperation.⁶⁵ To this post-war development may also be added the agitation of the Mussalmans over the Khilafat question.

Gandhi lived for the liberation of humanity from exploitation, hunger, disease ignorance and mental and physical worries and miseries all over the world..⁶⁶ The realisation of truth formed the foundation of Gandhian thought.⁶⁷ People felt attracted to him by the force of his personality. "Few can meet him without submitting to his Charm."⁶⁸ He gave the

signal for the non-cooperation Campaign⁶⁹ to the British Government when in his letter of August 1, 1920 he drew the attention of the Viceroy to the Khilafat and the Punjab wrongs.⁷⁰ He preached non-cooperation assiduously and delivered great speeches on its merits in various parts of the country, and week by week, articles appeared in *Young India* explaining it and answering objections.⁷¹

In the regular session of the Congress held in December 1920 at Nagpur, C.R. Das with Bengal delegation and Khaparde and Kelkar with maharashtrian representatives opposed the programme of non-violent and non-cooperation⁷² but they were patriots to the core and were easily persuaded to yield to the Gandhian programme of opposing the British might. C.R. Das was only sceptical as to the capacity of the people to carry it out⁷³ but he went to the length of moving the non-cooperation resolution in the open Congress⁷⁴ which emphasised that the existing Government of India had forfeited the confidence of the countrymen.⁷⁵ The Gandhian way prevailed.

Gandhi Opposed by Bengal Nationalist Leaders

Hindu elite, which led the nationalist movement in Bengal, the events and decisions of 1920 called into question the basic values of their social and political position. They were faced with the emergence of a new leader (Gandhi) whose philosophy of politics was diametrically opposed to their own at crucial points, and, simultaneously, with an attack on their social ascendancy from aspiring groups beneath them in Bengal society. As a consequence, they were forced, perhaps for the first time, to examine the foundations upon which their separate group identity⁷⁶ rested, and to defend their conception of the social order.⁷⁷ On 23 December 1919, the royal assent was given to the Government of India Bill. The extremists had steadfastly rejected all British reform proposals and their condemnation of those who were prepared to co-operate with the British, but they could contend, with some degree of truth, that this had been a strategem designed to force the British to yield more power.⁷⁸ That game was played out and the only result of the continued refusal to participate in constitutional politics would be the loss of the field constituting a tribe of timid, little-souled people who will think of themselves first and of their country last or not at all.⁷⁹ Even under the Morley-Minto constitution, the Extremists had qualms about leaving the legislative councils to the Moderates⁸⁰ and the danger seemed greater now that some of the functions of the provincial Governments were to be transferred to Indian Ministers.

No matter what concessions had been conceded to Indian demands, the British bureaucracy was still in command, and the extremists felt the Amritsar tragedy of April 1919

had shown that it was reactionary as ever. Motilal Ghose wrote, "If the fountain remains as it is, the addition of a few more conduits will not make the water any more drinkable than it was."⁸¹ What was needed was a change of heart, and this had not happened. The racial arrogance which had characterised British Indian policy in the past had been in evidence throughout the reform discussions. Even the basic assumption upon which the Montagu Chelmsford scheme rested: that Indians had yet to learn the art of self-government, and its corollary: that they should be given constitutional protection against their ignorance, were considered offensive.⁸² To accept the reforms, even under protest, would be to acquiesce in the judgment of Indian inferiority and this would injure the growth of national self-confidence.⁸³ They vacillated for a year before finally rejecting the Montagu-Chelmsford constitution. The plenary meeting at Nagpur in December 1920 voted over-whelmingly for withdrawal of all co-operation with the British. Between Amritsar and Calcutta, Calcutta and Nagpur, there were some remarkable changes of mind, none more striking than those of the Bengalis.⁸⁴ At Amritsar the Bengal contingent led by Chittaranjan Das, Byomkes Chakravarti and Bipin Chandra Pal, voted against the reforms. At Calcutta they voted for them. At Nagpur they were all for non cooperation.⁸⁵ It was Gandhi who commanded the majorities at Amritsar and Calcutta, where the Bengal nationalists voted with the minority, and it was to Gandhi that they capitulated at Nagpur.⁸⁶

Gandhi had emerged in the first rank of nationalist leaders and it was at his instigation that the hartals of April 1919 in protest against the Rowlatt Acts had been organised. The nationwide response to his appeal was testimony to his extraordinary influence, but the violence which resulted, shocked him deeply,⁸⁷ He was convinced that without greater self-discipline India could not challenge the British, and for this reason he demanded that Congress accept the Montagu-Chelmsford constitution. To these, like the Bengalis, who argued that the 1919 Congress session at Amritsar should reiterate the earlier uncompromising resolutions on the reforms, he replied that this would be irresponsible if the Congress had nothing constructive to offer in their place.⁸⁸ Gandhi was convinced that after these demonstrations of British disregard for their feeling it would be degrading for Indians to maintain their contact with British imperialism.⁸⁹ He, therefore, set out to formulate a programme of non-cooperation which Congress could offer to the nation in place of the reforms. As a first step, he called for a reconciliation between religious communities and he took up the Khilafat issue as a means of cementing Hindu-Muslim unity.⁹⁰ Gandhi was adamant that self-government for India would be a travesty if the, mass of the people were not freed from the exploitation of capitalists, landholders and money lenders. The nationalist

movement had to be the people's movement, to benefit the mass of people. "I don't want Swaraj at the cost of depressed classes or any other classes for that matter,"⁹¹ he wrote. He, therefore, insisted that Congress demonstrate its concern for the welfare of the Indian poor by adopting a programme for economic rehabilitation.

Apart from having a rare ability to sway great masses of people, Gandhi was an astute politician, and throughout the first half of 1920, he was gathering around him an influential group of personal adherents on whose support he could rely when he put his programme of non-cooperation before Congress.⁹² Despite this, there remained powerful sections who were opposed to the adoption of the scheme and who were determined not to acquiesce in his domination of the nationalist movement. Foremost among these were the Bengali leaders : An obvious reason for their opposition, and the one most often cited, was that they saw Gandhi as a rival. Chittaranjan Das certainly aspired for national leadership and his frequent appearance on public platforms outside, in the preceding two years, had already won him a national reputation.⁹³ Personal rivalry aside, there was reason for the Bengal nationalist leaders to be apprehensive, for Gandhi made it clear that there would be no room for deserters in any political organisation which he commanded. He told a meeting of Muslims in 1920, "so long as you choose to keep me as your leader, you must accept my conditions, you must accept dictatorship and the discipline of martial law."⁹⁴ This was something new to Indian nationalism. Gandhi relied far less on the support of any one area and his ambition was to subordinate regional differences to his national plan.⁹⁵ This, the Bengal leaders were not in the least inclined to accept. Bengalis had enjoyed power in the nationalist movement for too long to be willing simply to abdicate on request.⁹⁶ Nor were they willing to have an outsider dictate the form and content of their provincial politics.⁹⁷ To Gandhis insistent demands for a strong central authority under his control, they replied that personal dictatorship in the nationalist movement and a rigidly uniform policy would stunt national development.⁹⁸ Bipin Chandra Pal wrote, "Blind reverence for Gandhiji's leadership would kill people's freedom of thought and would paralyse by the dead weight of unreasoning reverence their individual conscience."⁹⁹ All nationalist politicians in Bengal at that time, Extremist or Moderate, were *bhadralok* : 'respectable people'. The *bhadralok* were not a social class, economically or occupationally defined; they were a status group,¹⁰⁰ distinguished from other Bengali communities by their style of life and their sense of social propriety.¹⁰¹

Gandhi had been strongly influenced by the quietest doctrines of Jainism and

Vaishnavism, and it was one of the secrets of his mass appeal that he customarily used popular Vaishnava images, in his speeches. By many of the Bhadrakok, modern Vaishnavism was despised as a lower class survival of the obscurantist cults of medieval times.¹⁰² There was another more pragmatic reason why Gandhi's insistence on satyagraha was unwelcome to the Bengal leaders. It seemed, at least initially, to offer no prospect of a satisfactory engagement with the British. A resort to passive resistance was no doubt necessary on occasions for suppressed majority communities, but it was considered inappropriate for the bhadrakok who were a dominant minority. Their politicians demanded a form of political action which enabled them to exert themselves against their adversaries, the British, without endangering their hold on political life.¹⁰³ These requirements were met by legislative politics and terrorism, both of which provided opportunities to hit at the British and yet involved relatively few people. It was in these activities that the bhadrakok politicians were accustomed to engage. Thus Gandhi's insistence upon non-violence, as also his demand for a boycott of the legislative councils, threatened their political style.¹⁰⁴

His rationale for council boycott seemed absurd to most of the bhadrakok leaders. He was arguing that Congressmen should withdraw from legislative councils and the other institutions of British Indian government because those institutions were alien and imposed. To many Bengal Congressmen such an argument was non sense. In the past when they had boycotted the legislative councils, it was not because the councils were foreign-because they were based on the English parliamentary model instead of an indigenous Indian Model-but because they did not conform closely enough to the English Model, their powers being so severely limited. The bhadrakok wanted parliamentary self-government in Bengal, and, at least in part, terrorism was their protest against the British refusal to recognise the intensity of their desire or to admit their capacity for such a form of government.¹⁰⁵ This reveals the cultural gulf dividing Gandhi from the bhadrakok. Gandhi was as concerned as any Bengali with questions of courage, and he was offering satyagraha to Indians as a way to prove their courage while maintaining their cultural integrity.¹⁰⁶ Yet for the bhadrakok his exclusive emphasis on ahimsa and satyagraha offended dearly cherished values, and it was their cultural integrity which they felt to be threatened.

This threat was increased by Gandhi's espousal of the doctrine of 'creative crisis'.¹⁰⁷ He proclaimed that he and his followers would harness the enthusiasm and energy generated by his campaign, to clear away the alien debts which overlay Indian society. Only in this way he claimed, could national creativity be restored.¹⁰⁸ On the surface there was nothing novel

for Bengal in this. Attacks on 'Anglicisation' and appeals for a return to the 'strength and simplicity of true Bengal life', had been heard frequently from political platforms throughout the province in the preceding fifteen years,¹⁰⁹ but formerly the orators were bhadralok, often the most westernised elite politicians, men who valued the European elements in their culture too highly to consider acting on their own advice. Gandhi, on the other hand, had shown in his personal life that he meant what he said, and he was now insisting that all nationalists should follow his example. A return to simplicity of living to free the individual from the training of material possessions; the renunciation of all non-essentials; a total commitment to the struggle against foreign domination – these were Gandhi's demands.¹¹⁰ To the bhadralok leadership this was philistinism. They were passionately proud of the richness of their culture and were unconvinced that they should strip their life bare in this way. Tagore himself spoke from the heart of the bhadralok when he demanded rhetorically of Gandhi, "The mind, surely is not of less account than a length of cotton thread spun on the wheel."¹¹¹ In a series of public addresses in Calcutta in August 1921, on his return from an extended trip abroad, he protested against Gandhi's anti-intellectualism and narrowness of view. Let us not obscure our vision of the wider world with the dust raised by political passion. He said let us seek universal truth, for 'India's awakening is a part of the awakening of the world.'¹¹² Earlier he had written : "our present struggle to alienate our heart and mind from the West is an attempt at spiritual suicide ...Let us be rid of all false pride and rejoice at any lamp being lit in any corner of the world knowing that it is a part of the common illumination of our house."¹¹³ His attack brought Gandhi to Calcutta but discussions between the two men revealed 'a difference of temperament so wide that it was extremely difficult to arrive at a common intellectual understanding.'¹¹⁴

The Bengal Congressmen's memory of the anti-partition agitation was another difficulty with which Gandhi had to contend in his effort to win Bengal for non-cooperation. 1905 was uppermost in bhadralok mind as they faced the decision of 1920. Tagore remarked "I find our countrymen, are furiously excited about non-cooperation, it will grow into something like our Swadeshi movement in Bengal."¹¹⁵ Banerjee Wrote, "In Bengal we have passed through the stage of non-cooperation. We practised it in the days of the swadeshi movement and the anti-partition agitation. We were non-cooperators before the rest of India thought of it."¹¹⁶ As this suggests there was a certain satisfaction in the thought that the rest of India was now following a path which Bengal had trodden fifteen years before, but there was also an element of pique at the temerity of an outsider like Gandhi in bringing forward as his own inventions and under labels of his own choosing, the old methods of boycott, swadeshi

and national education. Nor were the bhadralok leaders at all certain that they wished to retrace their steps. The campaigns of the partition period had been exhilarating but, in retrospect, the risks that had been taken seemed very grave. For a cause as dear to Hindu bhadralok hearts, as the whisky of Bengal, those risks had been worthwhile. The anti-partition agitation had achieved its ultimate object and in Hindu bhadralok lore it was reckoned a great victory, but there were many secret doubts as to the efficacy of the political methods which had been used.¹¹⁷

It must be recognised that apart from their aversion there were real difficulties in the way of their leading a mass movement. The great bulk of the peasantry, who comprised 75 percent of Bengal's population were Muslims, and even with the low-caste Hindus who made up the rest of the Hindu bhadralok heard little in common. In an editorial published on the eve of the special Congress session in Calcutta in September 1920, the Bengali declared : 'we Bengalis are opposed to non-cooperation. For a period of 10 years, from 1906 to 1916, we played the game. And we are not prepared to take back what we rejected on deliberation then. Even Gandhi had admitted that to act upto this resolution would mean rebellion and revolution, and we are not ready to proceed to such a course.'¹¹⁸ The Bengali was generally regarded as a voice of the Moderate party,¹¹⁹ but on this occasion, its concern at the effects of mass agitation was shared by a wide range of Bengal nationalists, Extremists as well as Moderates.¹²⁰ They were apprehensive that mass agitation would lead to violence against the socially privileged. The Hindu bhadralok elite was afraid of the social consequences of a disturbance of the established political order.¹²¹ It must be recognised that their fear was largely a fear of the unknown. They did not understand the 'masses' and they felt no confidence in their ability to lead or even control them should the existing order of political and social relationship be shaken. Their fear was blind but it was not unreasonable. A leap into the political unknown could well be a leap into revolution and anarchy.¹²²

The events of years immediately preceding 1930 had given the Hindu bhadralok politicians little reason for confidence. The war of 1914-18 had a profoundly unsettling effect on Bengali society and this social unrest was aggravated in the immediate post war years by economic difficulties. A succession of natural disasters in 1918 and 1919, including the great influenza epidemic, led to an extraordinarily sharp rise in the prices of foodstuffs and cotton goods,¹²³ and early in 1920 a severe slump brought to an end five year boom in Calcutta trade and industry.¹²⁴ Already there had been serious labour trouble in Bombay;¹²⁵ there were disturbing rumours of peasant unrest in the United Province and Bihar,¹²⁶ and

strikes among the migrant industrial workers of Howrah and Hooghly – side were becoming distressingly frequent.¹²⁷

The Calcutta Muslim riots of September 1918 had shown how much inflammable social material was now available in Bengal for political incendiaries, and the concern of the bhadrakok elite at this development had been manifest in the support accorded by the Hindu newspapers to the Government in its use of force to suppress the disorders.¹²⁸ This incident had also underlined the fact a distressing fact for the Hindu Bhadrakok-that in Bengal it was Muslim rather than Hindu politicians who would best make use of a mass appeal. Late in 1919 Khilafat countries had been established in various parts of Bengal 'to circulate news on the Moslem world,¹²⁹ and the official peace celebrations in December had provided their organisers with an opportunity to incite communal feeling against the British. The dangerous possibilities of exploitation of religious fanaticism and ignorance were evident to the Hindu Bhadrakok leaders, and when Gandhi urged them to support the Khilafat movement in order to cement Hindu-Muslim unity, they angrily protested against his encouragement to such a campaign.¹³⁰ The Bengal Congressmen found it objectionable that Gandhi should insist upon coupling a communal issue of this kind with non-cooperation and accord to men like Azad a place of prominence in his movement. It strengthened their conviction that his campaign was fraught with danger.¹³¹

Gandhi himself was aware of the importance of distinction between nationalism and social radicalism. He said, "In fighting the Government the motives of co-workers can be mixed. In fighting the devil of untouchability, I have absolutely select company."¹³² Gandhi was not simply offering a fight against the Government. He was also calling for an attack on the devils in Indian society, and the socially conservative Hindu Bhadrakok politicians were convinced that these devils should be left well alone lest all hell be let loose.¹³³

As the year passed and Gandhi's following grew, many of the Bengal politicians decided that they would have to consent to be led. 'The whole country is with Mr. Gandhi, but the politicians are holding back; yet one by one they are obliged to declare themselves' reported Andrews early in September.¹³⁴

By that stage Gandhi, a master of political tactics, had maneuvered his opponents into a corner. In April and May, he had arranged for the Central Khilafat Committee and the All India Congress Committee to discuss non-cooperation, and it was announced that a special session of Congress would be held in September to decide for or against the Scheme. In the meantime, he went ahead with his own preparations and on 1 August began personal non-

cooperation.¹³⁵ This forced the provincial Congress committees to reach some decisions and, with the knowledge that overt opposition to Gandhi would bring down upon them public wrath, they could do no more than search for some form of compromise. The Bengal Committee decided for non-cooperation in principle but urged that the legislative councils should be boycotted from within.¹³⁶ All the leading Bengali Extremists were candidates for the first elections for the new legislatures to be held at the end of the year, but the uncertainty as to the policy which Congress would adopt was a handicap to them in their canvassing. Worse still their advocacy of council entry, even if the purpose were to obstruct from within, put them perilously close to the Moderates – and that was to court political disaster.

They went to the September Congress in this awkward, compromised situation, while Gandhi, well aware of his strength, went full of confidence. The main debate on non-cooperation took place in the subjects committee. For three days the Bengalis struggled vainly to swing the majority against Gandhi, who was obdurate in his insistence that Congress give immediate support to every item of his programme. When his resolution came before the full session on the 8th, Bipin Chandra Pal moved an amendment to accept the principle but delay the implementation of non-cooperation. His concern, he explained, was to avoid failure on a national scale such as had occurred in Bengal during the swadeshi campaign of the partition period. In the voting on the following day, Pal's amendment was rejected and Gandhi's resolution carried by a large majority, against the votes of all but a handful of the Bengal delegates.¹³⁷

The old-style Congress, a federation of provincial grandees, was being destroyed by Gandhi's consolidation of the powers of the All-India Congress executive and his intrusions into provincial politics.¹³⁸ His new appeals had won him the support of the social groups which previously had no share in nationalist politics. The dynamics underlying the emergence of these were unclear but there were significant Indian social change in the second decade of the twentieth century. Gandhi drew his most solid support from areas which formerly had played no major part in the nationalist movement, and, in the old nationalist regions, from social groups which had formerly no voice in nationalist policy.¹³⁹ The elite were uncomfortable with the new language and symbolism of mass politics which Gandhi had introduced to Indian nationalism.¹⁴⁰ The elite resisted Gandhi's ambition to use the extended powers of a reconstructed Congress to achieve his vision.

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